

On entanglement

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1 Intro

One of the postulates of Complete Relativity[1] (CR) is that everything is entangled on some scale. Here I hypothesize that this is generally spin entanglement of souls.

2 Soul entanglement (quantum spin entanglement)

I have previously hypothesized that chirality of particles is a 2nd order spin, or angular momentum contained within its spin momentum.

Note that this is also implied with relativity of elementary particles - each spin momentum must contain other momentums of smaller scale.

Spin of a soul has a likely physical interpretation (incarnation) in sex of a body, while chirality in gender.

Since general oscillation in CR is not limited absolutely, but relatively, this enables everything to be entangled with everything over all space/time, although effectively (relatively) this will never be the case.

The strength of entanglement is thus inversely proportional to the order of oscillation (magnitude of resonance) - scale of spin momentum.

Generally, 1st order entanglement will be entanglement between equal species (at least in body, entangled souls may generally be particle/anti-particle pairs) due to equal scale of major gravitational maximums.

While 2nd order entanglement may also exist between equal species (representing a weaker entanglement), a 2nd order scale of one species may be a 1st order (major) maximum of other species, enabling inter-species entanglement.

Note that general oscillation implies relativity of a [scale of] major maximum - thus, souls generally oscillate between different scales (species).

References

- [1] Complete Relativity: Nature of Observables (2021), Amenoum
https://amenoum.org/complete_relativity.html